

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 118

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 118

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 118:1 "Give thanks to the LORD, for ^bHe is good; For His lovingkindness is everlasting. ² Oh let "Israel say, "His lovingkindness is everlasting." ³ Oh let the "house of Aaron say, "His lovingkindness is everlasting." ⁴ Oh let those "who ¹fear the LORD say, "His lovingkindness is everlasting."</p>	<p>Psa. 118:1 הודו ליהוה כי טוב כי לעולם תסדו : ² יאמרנא ישׂראל כי לעולם תסדו : ³ יאמרו-נא בית-אֶהֱרֹן כי לעולם תסדו : ⁴ יאמרו-נא יִרְאֵי יְהוָה כי לעולם תסדו : ⁵ מִן-הַמִּצַּר קראתי יה עֲנֵנִי בַּמִּרְתָּב יה : ⁶ יהוה לי לא אִירָא מִה-יַעֲשֶׂה לי אָדָם : ⁷ יהוה לי בְּעִזְרִי וְאֲנִי אֶרְאֶה בְּשִׁנְאֵי : ⁸ טוב לַחֲסוֹת בִּיהוָה מִבִּטָּח בָּאָדָם : ⁹ טוב לַחֲסוֹת בִּיהוָה מִבִּטָּח בַּנְּדִיבִים : ¹⁰ כָּל- גוֹיִם סָבְבוּנִי בְּשֵׁם יְהוָה כי אֲמִילָם : ¹¹ סְבוּנִי גַם-סָבְבוּנִי בְּשֵׁם יְהוָה כי אֲמִילָם : ¹² סְבוּנִי כְּדַבּוּרִים דַּעְכוּ כְּאֵשׁ קוֹצִים בְּשֵׁם יְהוָה כי אֲמִילָם : ¹³ דַּחַתָּה דַּחִיתַנִּי לַנֶּפֶל וַיהוָה עֲזָרַנִּי : ¹⁴ עֲנֵי וּזְמַרְתָּ יה וַיהִי-לִי לִישׁוּעָה : ¹⁵ קוֹל אֲרָנָה וַיִּשׁוּעָה</p>
<p>Psa. 118:5 From <i>my</i> "distress I called upon ¹the LORD; ¹The LORD answered me <i>and</i> ^bset me in a large place. ⁶ The LORD is "for me; I will ^bnot fear; "What can man do to me? ⁷ The LORD is for me "among those who help me; Therefore I will ^blook <i>with satisfaction</i> on those who hate me. ⁸ It is "better to take refuge in the LORD Than to trust in man. ⁹ It is "better to take refuge in the LORD Than to trust in princes.</p>	
<p>Psa. 118:10 All nations "surrounded me;</p>	

In the name of the LORD I will surely ^bcut them off.

¹¹ They ^asurrounded me, yes, they surrounded me;

In the name of the LORD I will surely cut them off.

¹² They surrounded me ^alike bees;

They were extinguished as a ^bfire of thorns;

In the name of the LORD I will surely cut them off.

¹³ You ^apushed me violently so that I ¹was falling,

But the LORD ^bhelped me.

¹⁴ ^{1a}The LORD is my strength and song,

And He has become ^bmy salvation.

Psa. 118:15 The sound of ^ajoyful shouting and salvation is in the tents of the righteous;

The ^bright hand of the LORD does valiantly.

¹⁶ The ^aright hand of the LORD is exalted;

The right hand of the LORD does valiantly.

¹⁷ I ^awill not die, but live,

And ^btell of the works of ¹the LORD.

¹⁸ ¹The LORD has ^adisciplined me severely,

But He has ^bnot given me over to death.

Psa. 118:19 ^aOpen to me the gates of righteousness;

I shall enter through them, I shall give thanks to ¹the LORD.

²⁰ This is the gate of the LORD;

בְּאֵהָלַי צְדִיקִים יְמִין יְהוָה
עֲשֵׂה חַיִּל : ¹⁶ יְמִין יְהוָה רֹמְמָה

יְמִין יְהוָה עֲשֵׂה חַיִּל : ¹⁷ לֹא

אָמוֹת כִּי־אֶתִּיה אֲסַפֵּר מִעֲשֵׂי

יְהוָה : ¹⁸ יִסַּר יִסְרָנִי יְהוָה וְלִפְנוֹת לֹא

נִתְנַנְּנִי : ¹⁹ פִּתְחוּ־לִי שַׁעֲרֵי־צֶדֶק

אֲבֹא־בָם אֲוֹרֶה יְהוָה : ²⁰ זֶה־

הַשַּׁעַר לַיהוָה צְדִיקִים יָבֹאוּ

בּוֹ : ²¹ אֲוֹרֶךְ כִּי עֲנִיתַנִּי וַהֲתִי־

לִי לִישׁוּעָה : ²² אֲבֵן מֵאֲסוֹ

הַבּוֹנִים הִיְתָה לְרֹאשׁ פִּנָּה : ²³

מֵאֵת יְהוָה הִיְתָה זֹאת הִיא

נִפְלְאֵת בְּעֵינֵינוּ : ²⁴ זֶה־הַיּוֹם

עֲשֵׂה יְהוָה נִגִּילָה וְנִשְׂמַחְתָּ בּוֹ :

²⁵ אָנָּה יְהוָה הוֹשִׁיעָה נָּא אָנָּה

יְהוָה הַצְּלִיתָה נָּא : ²⁶ בְּרוּךְ

הַבָּא בְּשֵׁם יְהוָה בְּרַכְנוּכֶם

מִבֵּית יְהוָה : ²⁷ אֵל אֵלֵי יְהוָה וַיֵּאָר

לָנוּ אֶסְרוּ־תָג בַּעֲבַתִּים עַד־

קָרְנוֹת הַמִּזְבֵּחַ : ²⁸ אֵלֵי אֲתָה

וְאֲוֹרֶךְ אֵלֵהִי אֲרוֹמְמֶךָ : ²⁹ הוֹדוּ

לַיהוָה כִּי־טוֹב כִּי לְעוֹלָם חֲסִדּוֹ :

The ^arighteous will enter through it.

²¹ I shall give thanks to You, for You have ^aanswered me,

And You have ^bbecome my salvation.

Psa. 118:22 The ^astone which the builders rejected

Has become the chief corner *stone*.

²³ This is ¹the LORD'S doing;

It is marvelous in our eyes.

²⁴ This is the day which the LORD has made;

Let us ^arejoice and be glad in it.

²⁵ O LORD, ^ado save, we beseech You;

O LORD, we beseech You, do send ^bprosperity!

²⁶ ^aBlessed is the one who comes in the name of the LORD;

We have ^bblessed you from the house of the LORD.

²⁷ ^aThe LORD is God, and He has given us ^blight;

Bind the festival sacrifice with cords ¹to the ^ahorns of the altar.

²⁸ ^aYou are my God, and I give thanks to You;

You are my God, ^bI extol You.

²⁹ ^aGive thanks to the LORD, for He is good;

For His lovingkindness is everlasting.

References

Psalm 118:1

^a1 Chr 16:8, 34; Ps 106:1; 107:1; Jer 33:11

^b2 Chr 5:13; 7:3; Ezra 3:11; Ps 100:5; 136:1-26

Psalm 118:2

^aPs 115:9

Psalm 118:3

^aPs 115:10

Psalm 118:4

¹Or *revere*

^aPs 115:11

Psalm 118:5

¹Heb *YAH*

^aPs 18:6; 86:7; 120:1

^bPs 18:19

Psalm 118:6

^aJob 19:27; Ps 56:9; Heb 13:6

^bPs 23:4; 27:1

^cPs 56:4, 11

Psalm 118:7

^aPs 54:4

^bPs 54:7; 59:10

Psalm 118:8

^a2 Chr 32:7, 8; Ps 40:4; 108:12; Is 31:1, 3; 57:13; Jer 17:5

Psalm 118:9

^aPs 146:3

Psalm 118:10

^aPs 3:6; 88:17

^bPs 18:40

Psalm 118:11

^aPs 88:17

Psalm 118:12

^aDeut 1:44

^bPs 58:9; Nah 1:10

Psalm 118:13

¹Or *fell*

^aPs 140:4

^bPs 86:17

Psalm 118:14

¹Heb *YAH*

^aEx 15:2; Is 12:2

^bPs 27:1

Psalm 118:15

^aPs 68:3

^bEx 15:6; Ps 89:13; Luke 1:51

Psalm 118:16

^aEx 15:6; Ps 89:13

Psalm 118:17

¹Heb *YAH*

^aPs 6:5; 116:8, 9; Hab 1:12

^bPs 73:28; 107:22

Psalm 118:18

¹Heb *YAH*

^aPs 73:14; Jer 31:18; 1 Cor 11:32; 2 Cor 6:9

^bPs 86:13

Psalm 118:19

¹Heb *YAH*

^aIs 26:2

Psalm 118:20

^aPs 15:1, 2; 24:3-6; 140:13; Is 35:8; Rev 22:14

Psalm 118:21

^aPs 116:1; 118:5

^bPs 118:14

Psalm 118:22

^aMatt 21:42; Mark 12:10, 11; Luke 20:17; Acts 4:11; Eph 2:20; 1 Pet 2:7

Psalm 118:23

¹Lit *from the LORD*

Psalm 118:24

^aPs 31:7

Psalm 118:25

^aPs 106:47

^bPs 122:6, 7

Psalm 118:26

^aMatt 21:9; 23:39; Mark 11:9; Luke 13:35; 19:38; John 12:13

^bPs 129:8

Psalm 118:27

¹Lit *unto*

^{a1} Kin 18:39

^bEsth 8:16; Ps 18:28; 27:1; 1 Pet 2:9

^cEx 27:2

Psalm 118:28

^aPs 63:1; 140:6

^bEx 15:2; Is 25:1

Psalm 118:29

^aPs 118:1

Targum

Psa. 118:1 Sing praise in the presence of the LORD, for he is good, for his goodness is forever. ² Let Israel now say, “For his goodness is forever.” ³ Let the house of Aaron now say, “For his goodness is forever.” ⁴ Let those who fear the LORD now say, “For his goodness is forever.” ⁵ Out of distress I called to Yah, Yah accepted my prayer in a broad place. ⁶ The word of the LORD is my help, I will not fear, what will a son of man do to me? ⁷ The word of the LORD is helping me, and I will behold, vengeance on my foes. ⁸ It is better to trust in the word of the LORD than to rely on a son of man. ⁹ It is better to trust in the word of the LORD than to rely on rulers. ¹⁰ All the Gentiles have surrounded me; in the name of the word of the LORD I have put my trust, for I will tear them apart. ¹¹ They have encompassed me, indeed, surrounded me; in the name of the word of the LORD I have put my trust, for I will tear them apart. ¹² They have encompassed me like hornets; they burned like fire in thorns; in the name of the word of the LORD I have put my trust, for I will tear them apart. ¹³ But you have knocked me down to make me fall; and the word of the LORD has given me help. ¹⁴ My strength and my praise are fearful against all the world; the LORD gave command by his word, and has become my redeemer. ¹⁵ The sound of praise and redemption is in the tents of the righteous; the right hand of the LORD has done mightily. ¹⁶ The right hand of the LORD is exalted; the right hand of the LORD has done mightily. ¹⁷ I will not die, for I will live, and I will tell of the deeds of God. ¹⁸ Truly, has Yah punished me, but he did not hand me over to death. ¹⁹ Open to me the entrances of the city of righteousness; I will enter them, I will praise Yah. ²⁰ This is the entrance of the sanctuary of the LORD; the righteous will enter by it. ²¹ I will give thanks in your presence, for you have received my prayer, and become for me a redeemer. ²² The child the builders abandoned was among the sons of Jesse; and he was worthy to be appointed king and ruler. ²³ “This has come from the presence of the LORD,” said the builders; “it is wonderful before us,” said the sons of Jesse. ²⁴ “This day the LORD has made,” said the builders; “let us rejoice and be glad in it,” said the sons of Jesse. ²⁵ “If it please you, O LORD, redeem us now,” said the builders; “if it please you, O LORD, prosper us now,” said Jesse and his wife. ²⁶ “Blessed is he who comes in the name of the word of the LORD,” said the builders; “they will bless you from the sanctuary of the LORD,” said David. ²⁷ “God, the LORD, has given us light,” said the tribes of the house of Judah; “bind the child for a festal sacrifice with chains until you sacrifice him, and sprinkle his blood on the horns of the altar,” said Samuel the prophet. ²⁸ “You are my God, and I will give thanks in your presence; my God, I will praise you,” said David. ²⁹ Samuel answered and said, “Sing praise, assembly of Israel, give thanks in the presence of the LORD, for he is good, for his goodness is everlasting.”

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The Sage Radak saw two levels of interpretation for this Psalm. At the personal level, David expresses his relief that Saul's persecution of him ends with Saul's death. David also envisioned the improvements he wanted to make for the nation. At a national level, this Psalm reflects the joy by which Israel will experience at the final redemption. Israel will return to its former glory and some of the old traditions and institutions will be restored.

Verse one through four

The Psalmist acknowledges that the lovingkindness of the LORD from the Sefirah Chesed will last throughout all time.

Acknowledge it to the LORD that the Sefirah Chesed will send his lovingkindness forever.

Say it now O Israel, that the Sefirah Chesed endures forever.

Say it now, O House of Aharon that the Sefirah Chesed endures forever.

Say it now, I those who fear the LORD that the Sefirah Chesed endures forever.

Verse nineteen and twenty

The Psalmist is referring to the fifty gates.

“Fifty Gates of Understanding were created in the world, and 49 were give to Moshe Rabbeinu. (Rosh Hashanah 21b)

The “Fifty Gates of Understanding” represent 50 spiritual channels, if you will, through which the Divine light of understanding makes its way from the upper realm to the lower realms. The gates themselves are the basis of all of Torah, and just achieving a few of the “gates” would make one a wise person. Receiving 49 of the 50 gates is beyond our present level of comprehension, but suffice it to say that it would, and did, make Moshe Rabbeinu other-worldly: Rebi Noson says: The intention of the Torah was that [Moshe] might be purged of all food and drink in his bowels so as to make him equal to the ministering angels. (Yoma 4b)

The so-called burial place of Moshe Rabbeinu itself bears witness to an even greater accomplishment. The Torah tells us where Moshe Rabbeinu was buried:

And Moshe went up from the plains of Moav to Mount Nevo, [to the] top of the summit facing Jericho. (Devarim 34:1)

Was “Nevo” merely the name of the mountain? Apparently it tells us more than the physical location of Moshe Rabbeinu’s burial:

Before his death he merited the 50th gate [of understanding], as it says, “To Mt. Nevo” (Devarim34:1): Nun Bo; the Nun entered his name and it became Neshamah. (Kehillas Ya’akov)

In other words, the letter Nun, which represents the number 50 and the level of Divine light associated with it, became a part of Moshe’s name, which is spelled

Moshe-Shin-Heh. With the addition of the letter Nun from the Nun Sha'arei Binah—the Fifty Gates of Understanding—the word can spell “Neshamah,” the third highest level of soul that we can access at this time.”¹

Open for me the gates of righteousness; I will enter into them and acknowledge God.

This gate is the LORD's, the righteous shall enter into it.

¹ Rabbi Pinchas Winston, “Fifty Gates of Understanding,” Torah.org, October 1, 2014, <https://torah.org/torah-portion/perceptions-5775-zoshabracha/>.

Appendix

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Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

